

Clamchowder: Connecting natural form and spatial structures with *Bivalvia* as a target

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Abstract

Biomimetics is a topic that has been attracting attention in the field of architectural engineering in recent years. We have researched utilizing the features of *Bivalvia* shell form, which are easy to imagine as a spatial structure and are thought to be a form optimized through their evolution, in structural systems. Mathematical models express the form of seashells, and one of these is the Ubukata model, which was proposed specifically for *Bivalvia*. We used this model and a model created from computed tomography (CT) images to identify the parameters of the mathematical model. In addition, we performed geometric and mechanical analysis on both models and compared them. In carrying out this research, I developed an application that makes it easier to research the shell of *Bivalvia*. Building this application as an extension tool of Grasshopper has improved compatibility with architectural engineering research. This application can create a point cloud of *Bivalvia* shell form by inputting a CT image or a simple oval shape as the aperture and setting a few parameters. Combining it with packages within Grasshopper that enable mechanical analysis and optimization, we can perform research focusing on the shells of *Bivalvia* more easily. Furthermore, Rhinoceros can output with many file types, so it is possible to use the output data with other software. This tool is planned to add more functions to support development research focusing on collaboration with the morphology of seashells and structure engineering.

Keywords: biomimetics, seashell, spatial structure, form-finding, metaethical model, Grasshopper

1. Introduction

There is a growing trend towards focusing on nature in the structural engineering field of architecture [1] – [3]. The research topic of creating better engineering technology by mimicking the form and system of nature is called “Biomimetics” [4]. It has been a popular topic in various engineering fields for a long time. In the field of architectural design and environmental engineering, wonderful works have been built by imitating natural systems and forms in the past [5] – [7]. Such works have also existed obviously in structural engineering for a long time. However, many of them are merely decorative or symbolic, with only a few being integrated into the core design of the structural system. On the other hand, in fields such as mechanical engineering including origami engineering and material science, Biomimetics often leads to essential technological innovation [8] – [10]. Even in the design of the flow of forces in constructions, if we can effectively learn from nature and imitate its essence, there is a high possibility that technological innovation will be born. Indeed, the natural world is full of forms that remind us of symbolic buildings, including spatial structures.

Seashells have been the focus of our study among the various forms found in nature. The shells that protect mollusks are also referred to as their homes, and they are believed to have evolved into the most suitable shapes for their survival. In particular, the shells of *Bivalvia* easily bring to mind spatial structures and domes, and are also said to be the origin of our field “shell structure”. In addition, molluscs are animals that have been studied from many perspectives, including biology and taxonomy, and there is a lot of scientific knowledge about them. There are also many different types, so it is possible

to select the most suitable type for various situations and issues. With applications to architectural structures engineering in mind, we are examining the geometric and mechanical properties of the shapes of *Bivalvia* shells with these characteristics [11][12]. In these studies, analytical models that accurately reproduce the shapes of the actual shell of *Bivalvia*, created using X-ray computed tomography (CT) images, were utilized. While this method allows us to verify the geometric characteristics of the seashell shape fully, there are problems such as the difficulty of obtaining specimens for CT imaging depending on any species, and the fact that many processes are required to create a model for analysis from CT images.

In this study, I have developed a tool that makes it easier to use the shapes of various *Bivalvia* as analysis models for geometric and mechanical analysis and more. In morphology, research is being conducted on mathematical models, which express the shape of a seashell using mathematical formulas [13] – [16]. For the shell of *Bivalvia*, a mathematical model also has been proposed that can express a wide range of shapes by giving several parameters. By integrating this mathematical model as a Grasshopper [17] component and making it available for use in Rhinoceros [18], a 3D modeling tool, it will be possible to more easily create 3D models for analysis that reproduce the seashell shape of *Bivalvia*. Rhinoceros is software commonly used in architectural design, and it is important to provide a tool that enables the creation of seashell shapes within this software. The aim is to promote the idea and innovation that natural forms can be used in architectural and structural design, using the shapes of seashells as a target in this tool development.

2. Contents of the developed tool

The tool includes three contents as shown in Figure 1. One is the application which is .exe file, and the others are two components for Grasshopper which is .gh file.

Figure 1: The structure of the development tool in this paper.

The application creates input data from a CT image as coordinates of the shape of a target seashell's aperture. The mathematical model used by this tool to generate the shape of *Bivalvia* uses the aperture shape of *Bivalvia* as the input data. While it is easy to generate seashell shapes giving simple geometric shapes such as circles or ellipses as input data, it is possible to generate seashell shapes that are more realistic to actual seashells giving the seashell's aperture shape from the CT image of seashells obtained in previous researches as input data. This application was developed for that purpose. This application was coded in Python and converted to a .exe file using the Pyinstaller library [19]. In the script that has been converted to .exe, the outline of the aperture of the seashell is detected from the brightness values of the CT images using Open CV [20], a general image processing library in Python. The detected aperture is captured as the position of the pixel, and the numerical values of the X and Y coordinates of the position are stored as a text file and output. This is used as the input data for the component. One of the two components is the main part of the tool, which creates the shape of the seashell by the input data representing the shape of the aperture and setting several parameters. The algorithm for generating the shell shape of *Bivalvia* uses a mathematical model expressed using an incremental method proposed by Ubukata [16]. These components were coded in C# on Visual Studio using specialized templates that can be obtained online. This mathematical model and the parameters that need to be set will be explained in Section 3. This main component outputs the XYZ coordinates of the point cloud, respectively,

representing the shell shape of *Bivalvia*. The other component is to adjust the hinge part to make the output shape easier to use. When the mathematical model is used to generate the shell shape of *Bivalvia*, the hinge part protrudes slightly from the aperture interface compared to the whole. This often causes problems when using the generated shape in the next step such as analysis and conversion to a solid model, as it can become a singular point. In such cases, a component has been developed to remove this part.

3. Theory of seashell mathematical model on this tool

As aforementioned, this tool uses Ubukata model which is a mathematical model to generate the shell shape of *Bivalvia*. The method of expressing the shape of a shell using mathematical formulas has been actively discussed in the field of morphology for a long time. Section 3.1 introduces the background to this. Section 3.2 explains the mathematical theory of the Ubukata model and the parameters that need to be set to use this tool.

3.1. Mathematical model for seashell

The shells of many mollusks form highly regular spiral patterns, which can be described by logarithmic or equiangular helices. Descartes was the first to demonstrate that various natural phenomena are spiral-shaped. Later, Henry Moseley was credited with being the first to propose that the coiling of seashells also adheres to this principle [21]. In 1917, Thompson outlined four fundamental rules for spiral shells in *On Growth and Form* [22]. This concept would later become significant in representing seashells through mathematical models.

Based on the idea that the shape of a seashell can be expressed by integrating several rules based on a spiral, two important models; the Raup model [13] and the Okamoto model (Growing tube model) [15], were proposed in the middle of the 20th century. The mathematical models for seashells, based on these two models, are continually refined to more accurately replicate the shapes of various seashells [14][16]. The mathematical model used in this tool is the Ubukata model which is specific for *Bivalvia* based on the Okamoto model.

3.2. Ubukata model

This section describes the mathematical formulae of the Ubukata model [16]. Additionally, the parameters that can be configured in the tool are presented. This model is expressed in an incremental format. The basic formulae of the Ubukata model are

$$X_n = x_{n-1} + \mu \cdot \log_2 \frac{n'}{n} \cdot nv_{n-1}, \quad (1)$$

$$Y_n = y_{n-1} + \mu \cdot \log_2 \frac{n'}{n} \cdot bv_{n-1}, \quad (2)$$

$$Z_n = z_{n-1} + \mu \cdot \log_2 \frac{n'}{n} \cdot tv_{n-1}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mu = \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta s}, \quad (4)$$

$$x_n = x_o + (xp_n \cdot \cos(\theta) \cdot \cos(\rho) + yp_n \cdot \sin(\varphi) + zp_n \cdot \cos(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\rho)) \cdot \frac{n'}{n}, \quad (5)$$

$$y_n = y_o + (xp_n \cdot (-\cos(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\rho) - \sin(\theta) \cdot \sin(\rho)) + yp_n \cdot \cos(\theta) \cdot \cos(\varphi) + zp_n \cdot (-\cos(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\rho) + \sin(\theta) \cdot \cos(\rho)) \cdot \frac{n'}{n}, \quad (6)$$

$$z_n = z_o + (xp_n \cdot (\sin(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\rho) - \cos(\theta) \cdot \sin(\rho)) - yp_n \cdot \sin(\theta) \cdot \cos(\varphi) + zp_n \cdot (\sin(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\rho) + \cos(\theta) \cdot \cos(\rho))) \cdot \frac{n'}{n} \quad (7)$$

$$n_n = (n_{n-1} \cdot \cos(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\rho) + b_{n-1} \cdot \sin(\varphi) + t_{n-1} \cdot \cos(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\rho)) \cdot \frac{n'}{n}, \quad (8)$$

$$b_n = (n_{n-1} \cdot (-\cos(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\rho) - \sin(\theta) \cdot \sin(\rho)) - b_{n-1} \cdot \sin(\theta) \cdot \cos(\varphi) + t_{n-1} \cdot (-\cos(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\rho) + \sin(\theta) \cdot \cos(\rho))) \cdot \frac{n'}{n}, \quad (9)$$

$$t_n = (n_{n-1} \cdot (\sin(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \cos(\rho) - \cos(\theta) \cdot \sin(\rho)) - b_{n-1} \cdot \sin(\theta) \cdot \cos(\varphi) + t_{n-1} \cdot (\sin(\theta) \cdot \sin(\varphi) \cdot \sin(\rho) + \cos(\theta) \cdot \cos(\rho))) \cdot \frac{n'}{n}, \quad (10)$$

where

$$xp_n = X_n - x_o, \quad (11) \quad yp_n = Y_n - y_o, \quad (12) \quad zp_n = Z_n - z_o, \quad (13) \quad \Delta s = \log_2 \left(\frac{|n'|}{|n|} \right). \quad (14)$$

Here, μ means amplification and ε is parallel travel distance of the hinge portion.

The parameters for the angles in these formulae are as follows. To calculate these angles, three primary parameters of this model are required. By adjusting these three parameters, the shapes of various shells can be easily reproduced. θ is the angle of the shell bulge direction. φ and ρ are winding direction.

$$\theta = C \cdot \Delta s, \quad \varphi = T \cdot \Delta s, \quad \rho = V \cdot \Delta s. \quad (15)$$

Table 1 describes the meanings of these main parameters. In addition, Table 1 shows the parameters that can be set in the component that uses this tool to generate seashell shapes.

Table 1 Parameters of the Ubukata model that can be set in the component.

In the formulae	On the component	The meaning of each parameter
C	C	Degree of valve inflation on X direction.
T	T	Degree of valve inflation on Z direction.
V	V	Torsion
μ	m	$\varepsilon/\Delta s$: Amplification
n/n'	W	The integral of the generation curve.
-	SS	The incremental number of calculation cycles.

4. How to use Clamchowder

The developed tool was named ‘‘Clamchowder’’. Figure 2 is the logo of the tool. This tool has been made available on GitHub. Figure 3 shows a QR code linking to the download page [23]. In this section, the usage of Clamchowder is explained with examples. First, this section describes the basic usage of the application and the components, using the example of a *Fulvia mutica*. This section also describes what kind of shell shapes can output by adjusting the value for each parameter. Next, this section discusses how the output shapes can be applied in the architecture and structure engineering field and others.

Figure 2: The logo of the developed tool in this study; Clamchowder.

Figure 3: QR code linking to the download page for Clamchowder [23].

First, prepare the coordinates of the aperture. Draw an ellipse on Rhinoceros and divide it, or extract the coordinates of the aperture shape from the CT image using an executable file (.exe file) application. Please put the CT image with the opening you want to extract the shape of and this application in the

same folder, and then double-click the application after naming the CT image “aperture.tif”. A CT image showing the aperture's outline and text files containing the X and Y coordinate values are output. Figure 4 (a) shows the CT image that was loaded, and Figure 4 (b) shows the output image. CT images must have a .tif extension.

Figure 4: (a) CT images for extracting the shape of the aperture to be input and (b) the detected aperture shape.

Next, the main component that generates the shell shape of *Bivalvia* is used with the text file output by the application as the input data. Figure 5 shows the main component. Load the text files and connect the coordinates to “coodiX” and “coodiY” as shown in Figure 5. The remaining parameters that the component requires are shown in Table 1. Of the parameters not shown in Table 1, “Area” and “Ym” are needed for setting initial values of incremental calculations, and “openaxis” is already prepared for use when this tool is enhanced in the future. For “Area”, calculate and enter the area of the aperture, and for “Ym”, enter 0.5. “openaxis” requires 1.0 input, but this is scheduled to change in the future. The remaining parameters, C, T, and V, need to be adjusted by the user, and the resulting shape is determined based on these parameters. In addition, the number of iterations can be adjusted using the parameter SS. The real seashell grows through additive growth, and the mathematical model also grows through additive growth by iterations. Figure 6 shows the differences in shape generation for each number of iterations.

Figure 5: The main component of Clamchowder.

Figure 6: The difference in the generated shape when the number of input iterations is changed. The numbers input was increased in the order (a) to (d).

In the case of *Fluvia mutica*, these are set as shown in Table 2. These three parameters were optimized using the GA algorithm based on the actual shape from CT images [24]. Table 2 also shows the values used to express other different species. The three examples other than *Fluvia mutica* are examples of how adjusting each parameter will produce a particular shape. Figure 7 shows the results of shape generation for the species whose parameter values are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Parameters of the Ubukata model that can be set in the component.

Parameters	<i>Fluvia mutica</i>	Example 1	Example 2	Example 3
Input aperture	CT image	Ellipse	Perfect circle	Perfect circle
C	0.8974	0.0000	0.1500	0.1500
T	0.2188	0.1000	0.0000	0.0000
V	-0.1140	-0.5000	-0.3000	-0.3000
μ	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.3000
n/n'	1.01	1.05	1.05	1.05

Figure 7: The results of shape generation using the parameters shown in Table 2. (a) is *Fluvia mutica*, (b) is Example 1, (c) is Example 2, and (d) is Example 3. (-1) is the bird-eye view, (-2) is the plane view, and (-3) is the side view.

In addition, it is possible to delete excessive point groups in the hinge section due to excessive incremental calculations by using another component shown in Figure 8 (a) as a sub-component. As shown in Figure 8 (b)-1, the coordinates output by the main component are connected to the coordinate input point of this component, and by setting the deletion threshold, the point cloud at the corresponding is deleted as shown in Figure 8 (b)-2.

Figure 8: (a) The component for deleting excessive points and (b)-1 before and (b)-2 after using sub-component.

By adjusting the parameters, it is also possible to examine just changes in the shell shapes of *Bivalvia* that are generated as a point cloud, but many things become possible by combining this point cloud with other components. For example, a model with a shell shape of *Bivalvia* that possesses thickness and volume can be created by utilizing a component "ShrinkWrap" in Grasshopper. As shown in Figure 9, adding thickness makes 3D printing possible. Surfaces can be generated from point clouds and used for mechanical analysis of shapes. Furthermore, various components and plug-ins have been developed for Grasshopper, and their combination offers the potential to achieve simulations and study beyond what was originally envisioned by the author of this paper. Rhinoceros is also modeling software, and it is possible to output shapes created with various extensions. Using those files with other software will make even more things possible. It is also commonly used in architecture as CAD software, and this tool is expected to be particularly useful in architectural and structural design.

Figure 9: (a) Using "Shrink Wrap" allows users to create models with thickness. (b) It is also possible to make the surface of the model a mesh.

On the other hand, only this tool cannot create *Bivalvia* shells with a thickness distribution. It has been found that, among the geometric properties of *Bivalvia* shells, the thickness distribution has a significant effect on their mechanical properties [11]. Therefore, if it were possible to vary the thickness according to position, rather than just the shape, it would greatly aid in elucidating the relationship between mechanical and geometric properties of *Bivalvia*. However, it is difficult to assign thickness properties to the mathematical model of the incremental method itself. Therefore, first, I plan to evolve this tool so that the thickness distribution obtained from the actual shell of *Bivalvia* is reflected in each of the points that make up the point cloud, and with the help of other components, a point cloud with a thick shell shape of *Bivalvia* can be formed.

5. Conclusion

This paper described the background behind "Clamchowder", a shell shape of *Bivalvia* generation tool, and its purpose. It also explains how to create *Bivalvia* shapes using this tool and gives examples of how it can be used. As mentioned above, this tool aims to promote the idea and innovation of utilizing natural forms in architecture and structural design, using the shape of a shell as a target. It would be wonderful if this tool were used in various ways and more research and design were done using the shape of

Bivalvia as a target. This tool is still in the early stages of development. As mentioned in the previous section, there are plans to add functions such as adding thickness elements. It would also be appropriate to make it possible to generate shell shapes other than *Bivalvia*. I hope you will access the repository of "Clamchowder" using the QR code shown in Figure 3 and use this tool in your Rhinoceros and Grasshopper.

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